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The War on Ukraine and the Racist

Discourse: Political Reading

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Abstract

On 24 February 2022, the world populations woke up to hear the most terrible, not the only one, news in the 21st century. At early morning, the Russian troops trespassed the Ukrainian border to invade the latter. This happened after multiple different threats made by the Russian president Vladimir Putin. What is noteworthy is the fact that the Ukrainian plight received a thorough sympathy from different nations, even from the most deteriorated countries like Syria and Iraq. Irrespective of the individual compassion, the majority of world countries condemned this invasion. But the war on Ukraine verily contributed to revealing the most latent racist discourse. Having empathized with Ukraine does not really prove that the case is a humane issue but a European one, mostly ethnical one. Those who attempted to express their emotions towards what is happening to Ukraine, not all but some, were engaged in double standards when they compared Ukraine's plight to others in the Middle East. In this regard, I am to negotiate the racist comparisons between what is happening in the Middle East and Ukraine as well as the international hypocrisy.

Key words: Racism, Terrorism versus Heroism, Hypocrisy, Civilized Refugees and Uncivilized Refugees, They Are and Us.

Introduction

The demise of the Soviet Union traced an era of crumbling for Russia. It lost all the territories attached to before. However, with the rise of Vladimir Putin, the dream of restoring the bygone glory became prominent to all. This is due to the fact that the majority of the old Soviet Union's allies became either NATO members or EU's supporters. This is something the New Russia would not accept under any circumstances. Thus, the Ukraine's plight came out. Ukraine was, with due respect, a mistress that both EU and Russia are fond of. The competition furiously started among the two for either persuading Ukraine to join each of them or forcing it. As Demetri Trenin mentioned, "The Ukraine crisis was immediately preceded by competition between the EU and Russia for the future geoeconomic orientation of Ukraine. The roots of the crisis lie in the 2008 war between Russia and Georgia, which ended the prospect of enlargement of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) for both Georgia and Ukraine" (Trenin, 2014: 4). Based on Trenin's analysis, we are to admit that Russia invaded Georgia for fear of what might happen if NATO brought its forces to its land. And thus we can say that Putin invaded Ukraine for the same reason. But what we are interested in is what verily happened after the invasion. As being well known to all of us, the war brings only crumbing and suffering to humanity. This does not happen in Ukraine solely, but in other places in Middle East as well as elsewhere. What is noteworthy is not the invaded Ukraine, but the way most of peoples empathized with it indistinctively. Those people not only felt pity for what is going on currently in Ukraine, but they have been bitterly involved in what I shall call racist discourse, double standards, hypocritical narratives, and so forth.

1. The Ukrainian Plight and the Rise of Racial Discourse

It is undeniable that any war is tragic, not only human beings, for all creature. Therefore, it might be more logical and moral to empathize with certain people who are undergoing such circumstances, something we now can see in Ukraine. This is an unenviable situations that the people of Ukraine are exposed to. Since the war broke out between Russia and Ukraine, we have been confronted with rough and unjust statements being said about other people who are in a state of war, something similar to what Ukraine is experiencing. Trying to compare those people to Ukrainians, many racist reports have been made. An example of such racist statements was firstly made by CBS News senior correspondent in Kyiv Charlie D'Agata.

This isn't a place, with all due respect, like Iraq or Afghanistan that has seen conflict raging for decades. This is a relatively civilised, relatively European – I have to choose those words carefully, too – city where you wouldn't expect that, or hope that it's going to happen (Aljazeera, 2022).

The statements declared by D'Agata are full of emotions and sincerity towards Ukrainian people, but not humane at all. Based on his saying, we infer that the war is invented especially for those in the Middle East or Afghanistan. He made such inhumane statements only four days after the war had broken out. But comparing it to Afghanistan where the war really fatigued the Afghans is really unfair. When talking about empathizing with people of war, Iraqi people and the Afghans must come in mind because they were exposed to an imposed war. For the Afghans, they were firstly invaded by the Soviet Union and were secondly exposed to a harsh conquering operation by the Americans and its allies from NATO and elsewhere.

D'Agata was not the sole person to make such racist discourse, but the Ukraine's former deputy general prosecutor, David Skuarelidze also made an absolute alleged racist comparison between the Ukrainians and Others, I must call. Based on his

discourse, he found it “emotional” to “see European people with blonde hair and blue eyes being killed every day with Putin’s missiles...” (Aljazeera, 2022). What Skuarelidze implied means conspicuously that if you don’t have blue eyes and blonde hair, you deserve death. His statements can also be analyzed as if black people and brown ones don’t deserve empathy or, more roughly, they deserve war. It does not matter how much an individual is a white supremacist, but they must hide their emotions and feelings rather than dehumanizing others.

If someone thinks that these statements might come out from such racist persons only, they are wrong. The reason is that this racist discourse, met with the Ukrainian plight, was narrated in the entire Europe. Instances of such discriminated voices were also raised by a French one and a Britisher. On the one hand, we have the French journalist, Philippe Corbe, who indicated that they ‘are not talking about Syrians fleeing the bombing of the Syrian regime...”but talking “about Europeans leaving in cars that look like ours to save their live” (Aljazeera, 2022). On the other hand, we have Daniel Hannan who wrote in The Telegraph that war does not occur any more in poor and far away ‘populations” (Ibid). They are both made inappropriate views that must be condemned by anyone who pretends humanity. What I am surprised at is the fact that they are trying to teach us humanity while, in fact, they behave savagely. They came and invaded us and made us suffer many years of occupation under pretext of a civilizing mission, but now they show us how brutal they are.

Making such statements, these segregators are fully blind of the reality of how many people were victimized in Iraq, Yemen, and Chechnya. The war brought about by America in Iraq ‘resulted in 400,000 to 700,000 of deaths” (H. Akbar and Kisilowski, 2022). We did not see any emotions raised by Europeans against what the United States did in Iraq, but rather they reached their goal since they considered

that war as a kind of retaliation. Iraq was totally innocent since they found no Mass Destruction Weapons they pretended that Saddam Husain's regime had. They destroyed the country and, after that, they apologized that their CIA put them down. Does Iraq of today need such feeble statement?

In addition to Iraq where the war has already stopped, Yemen is still under attack by Saudi's regime supported by the United States. Higher than three hundred seventy seven thousands of Yemeni people died as a result of this prolonged war, but not any sanction was suggested against Saudi Arabia. So what is the difference between Russia and this regime?

When Putin invaded Ukraine, they turned the world upside down with their poor and futile political discourse, but when Putin regime invaded Chechnya, there was a formidable silence. When 80,000 of troops trespassed Chechnya's borders and more than fifty thousands of innocent people were perished, where were the United Nations, NATO, and EU? This is what we call double standards.

What D'Agata, Hannan, Corbe and many others raised of segregated sermons implies that the European people are suffering from Alzheimer's disease, since all of them forgot about the atrocities of the World War One and Two. It is obvious that these wars did not take place in Middle East but in the heart of so-called civilized Europe. Absolutely, D'Agata or Hannan, even Corbe would not argue that the nations where the war broke out included France, Belgium, Hungary, Austria, Serbia, ARussia, Britain, Germany, etc. were Arabs. In fact, the most transparent individuals would admit that Syria, Yamen, Afghanistan, Iraq, Lebanon, Libya, Sudan are not on the list. According to History, over than sixteen millions lives, of which children, old men, women, young men, and soldiers, were perished. Nine million soldiers were killed, twenty two millions, of which civilians and soldiers were wounded, and approximately ten millions of civilians were tragically killed

(History 2009). This is only the death toll of the World War one. Even if we calculate the casualties of victims in the whole Middle East, including Afghanistan and Chechnya, we would not be able to reach this horrific number of death. Imagine that all those dead people are in front of you, and imagine how terrific and uncivilized these atrocities are. Nevertheless, those new white supremacists are talking about Europe that never experienced peace since its establishment in an exaggeratingly civilized way.

2. Discriminatory Comparison between Arab-Muslim Refugees and Ukrainian Refugees

Once the war broke out in Ukraine, many of Ukrainians hastily started fleeing their country, either to Poland, Hungary, or Romania. These host countries welcomed the Ukrainian refugees in a warmth way we did not use to see with other people from different backgrounds, race, and ethnicity. While the Ukrainian refugees were welcomed warmly, Iraqis, Afghans, Palestinians, Syrians, Libyans, Lebanese, and many others were dehumanized by the same countries that received such tremendous number of Ukrainians. Of course, we are not against receiving Ukrainians in particular, but we only want other refugees to receive the same humane treatment.

Hungary that received and still receiving Ukrainian refugees raised many political discriminatory statements. When Hungary was questioned about why the Ukrainian refugees were welcomed while others from Syria, Afghanistan, and Iraq were refused, the answer was presented by the Bulgarian Prime Minister as follows: "These people are Europeans. These people are intelligent, they are educated people. ... This is not the refugee wave we have been used to, people we were not sure about their identity, people with unclear pasts, who could have been even terrorists ..." (Wamsley, 2022). We can infer from the answer given by Kiril Petkov that refugees coming from other places like Syria and Iraq are ignorant, backward, uneducated, savage, barbarian and useless.

Before touching on the discriminatory narrative made by Petkov, let us elaborate on his hypocritical politics. Only two months before the breaking out of war, Hungary was determined that they "are not going to let anyone in" of refugees, making "restrictive immigration policies" (Ibid). However, they

received many Ukrainians, and feeling honorable to embrace them. Conspicuously, these restrictive policies were taken only to constrain Syrian, Iraqi, and other refugee's movement.

Despite of the racist discourse that targeted Muslims and Arabs, Muslim leaders are still generous and more tolerant with the oppressed. It is obvious that Ukrainian people are innocent and being killed without any reasonable justification. Regardless to their deafening silence that was noticed when Muslims were being killed and kicked out of their countries, Muslims still say that the war is bad for the innocent whatever his or her sins are. With the entrance of Ramadan, Qatar asked for helping refugees without any segregation. This can be seen in Al-Qaradaghi's words:

“Thousands of people from Ukraine have become refugees. These people are just like the Syrians, Afghans, and Yemenis. They are running away from death. Nobody willingly leaves their country or home,” he said, adding that they struggle for survival on their way to migration (Bayar, 2022).

These sentences can reveal what the west is unable to do, that has not reached the level of being humane, to have the capacity to empathize with others, to put itself in the others' shoes. Frankly, we can say that the Islamic world has been always a home for the oppressed, but not as the west and America profile us to the world. This can be traced back to even the rise of Othman dynasty and even to now Turkey. For example, during nineteen century Jews were completely persecuted and oppressed by the Europeans. They were not considered even citizens in Europe. The places to where the Jews resorted were Islamic countries. A great number of the oppressed Jews were refugees in the Othman Empire that was at the time the house of every persecuted.

“Unfamiliar with the anti-Semitic movement, the Ottoman Empire was one of the few places in the world where Jews could live freely. In 19th century Europe, they lived in

harsh conditions, often in closed quarters called ghettos, and were deprived freedom of religion, holding public office and even the right to live. They were also denied the rights to acquire property, get an education, travel, and found printing houses and publishing newspapers” (Ekinci, 2017).

In the Othman Empire, the land that Jews would betray and stab in the back, were the whereabouts where Jews lived freely and practiced their religious rituals, since they did not have this chance in Europe or in another spot. Jews were not only persecuted in the 19th century, but we must take into consideration what Jews had to undergo when the Spaniards got back Andalusia from the Muslims there. In 1492, Sultan Bayezid II allowed tremendous number of Jews to resort to the Othman Empire, feeling the oppression in Spain. They settled in different places like Izmir and Istanbul (Ekinci, 2017). This evidently shows how tolerant Muslims were to refugees. Jews did not solely live freely in the Othman Empire, but they were also living luxuriously under the rule of Muslims in Andalusia before the Spanish authority came to reign. On contrary, Muslims refugees have been exposed to maltreatment and oppression by many countries worldwide. Even Jews that were thriving and prospering under the reign of Muslims, they occupied Palestine and oppressed the Muslims.

3. The Hero and the Terrorist

The political conflict between Russia and Ukraine raised the world populations' consciousness to look at Ukraine as the weak victim attacked and persecuted by the Russian devil. The dispute was no longer believed to be a political conflict brought about by the gluttony of Putin to contain Ukraine and prevent it of joining NATO, but it was looked at as a war between Beowulf and Grendel, the good and evil. What caught the world and especially Arab's attention was the congregation of what is so called good-Ukrainian citizens who fend for their land. Their nationalism was deemed as an act of heroism. But what attracted the attention at most was the presumable plight between the majority of Muslim world and Ukraine and the way the world dealt with both cases.

When India invaded Kashmir, imprisoned its leaders, and killed its heroes who attempted to defend their most disputed autonomous province, the world was completely deafened and muted. The then United States president did not dare to call Narendra Modi 'Killer' as Biden named Putin. Was not Kashmir independent as Ukraine and was conquered either? The eyes that did not look at Kashmir with empathy were suddenly opened and shed tears for Ukraine. This does not mean that Ukraine should not be empathized with, but the heart that welcomed refugees from Ukraine, and mouth that called Ukrainian defendants heroes should also do the same for the oppressed in Kashmir. No, the mouth that praised the heroic act of Ukrainians defending their land called Kashmiri heroes terrorists and dissidents. As Beydoun put it: "Kashmiri state leaders were jailed *en masse*, journalists and dissidents arrested, and men, women and children trying to defend their already precarious aspirations of self-determination have been wholly branded as terrorists" (2022).

The hypocritical narrative did not target only Kashmiri people, but also Palestinian and Yemeni people. Palestinians have been resisting the Israeli apartheid

regime that was founded on their blood and corpses and fighting for their freedom for seventy three years. However, no one considered this as an act of heroism and dignity, but most countries called them terrorists. Witnessing the Ukrainians' resistance of Putin, Paul Massaro expressed his feeling saying: "I'm racking my brain for a historical parallel to the courage and fighting spirit of the Ukrainians and coming up empty. How many people have ever stood their ground against an aggressor like this? It's legendary" (Mhawesh, 2022). This raises doubts whether Massaro has ever heard of Palestine or not, the nation that was served to Zionists in a golden plate by Belfour in 1917.

Conclusion:

The racial and hypocritical discourse that condemned Palestine, Yamen, and Kashmir *voices* the Ukrainian struggle and made their plight an international case. This reflects how Muslims worldwide are outcast and marginalized. Their voices are unheard even if they cry out so aloud. We never support oppression or injustice. We always counter the dictators and invaders. The same feeling we have towards Palestine, Kashmir, Yemen, Syria, Lebanon, Libya, Iraq and Myanmar, we have it towards Ukraine and other oppressed nations and people worldwide.

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